

Securing User Health Records: Leveraging Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) and Ethereum Integration for Enhanced Data Protection*

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Abstract—This study delves into the amalgamation of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) with Large Language Models (LLMs) and Ethereum blockchain technology to bolster the security and confidentiality of user health records within healthcare systems. The research explores the transformative potential of this technological fusion in fortifying data protection, controlling access, and ensuring transparency in the management of sensitive health data. By harnessing RAG's capacity for generating contextually pertinent responses, the linguistic prowess of LLMs, and the decentralized, tamper-resistant nature of Ethereum's blockchain, the investigation seeks to address the pressing imperative of safeguarding user health records in the digital era. The paper examines the anticipated advantages, obstacles, and ramifications associated with the deployment of this innovative strategy, underscoring the paramount significance of data security and privacy in healthcare environments.

Index Terms—LLM, Ethereum,RAG

I. INTRODUCTION

Storing medical records digitally is an essential application in the field of medical health care. There are multiple methods currently available in the market nowadays. Current medical records systems are just client-server systems where all of the data is stored in the server of the central entity which puts the user out of power. The user doesn't have ownership of his own medical data which is very personal and confidential in nature. To get access to the past health records we have at a certain medical hospital we have to go through a pile of forms and applications. This takes away the beauty of the technology which should act as an effective bridge that would serve us instead it makes it even more complicated and puts the user out of power and helpless to even access his own data. There are few decentralized solutions available but they are not yet that practical. The problem of data accessibility yet doesn't have a proper robust solution. Identifying this difference between the current systems and the users' needs, we with this paper propose a system that will once again put the user of the system in the power of his data. We are also trying to integrate the RAG with the documents of the user so that the user can chat with the documents.

A. A. AIM AND CONTRIBUTION

The primary objectives of this research paper are as follows:

1.3.1 To understand key features of etherium large language models and blockchain and retrieval augmented generation, and how they can be used to enhance health records of users.

1.3.2 To explore the potential benefits of integrating large language models, etherium and Llms in healthcare data management, including improved access control, transparency and data protection.

1.3.3 To identify and analyse the challenge....and regulatory ethical considerations To identify and analyse the challenges and limit issues associated with implementing llm's ,RAG and Ethereum Healthcare systems, focusing on technical and regulatory ethical considerations

1.3.4To propose a consensual framework for integrating llm's arrangement etherium healthcare data to manage and give more access to the user of their data, highlighting the potential for inner security and privacy. 1.3.5 Evaluate the potential impact of this integration on health care data management, including its data security implications, patient privacy and regulatory complex. .

B. B. METHODOLOGY

We first executed a literature survey on the multiple solutions to store medical records both centralized and decentralized approaches. This allowed us to gain an on-ground understanding of the current market scenario of the available solutions and market gaps. We further analyzed and compared different solutions specifically decentralized solutions which allowed us to map the gap between the solutions. This allowed us to build a foundational understanding of our proposed solution. Then we proposed an approach that will fill this gap and a solution that will store their records in a decentralized manner put them in power and allow them complete ownership of their personal medical data. Also, not all people are able to read their lab reports. So we are proposing the use of RAG Retrieval Augmented Generation that will allow the user to chat with the lab reports. The design of the solution involved designing of the architecture of the system using the current

tool. We also had to design multiple custom components and interfaces. We used the Mixtral and Gemini as our foundational models for our solution. Also the functionality provided by the langchain was utilized. The paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the Related works in this field. We then provide the reader with some preliminaries (Section III) on the topic of decentralized medical records. Section IV outlines the proposed model, including a solution that addresses the aimed contributions. The validation of the proposed model and solution, based on a real-world use case, is presented in Section V, Lastly, we discuss and conclude the paper with some future work direction in Sections VI and VII.

II. RELATED WORKS

There has been much research in the past few years on decentralized healthcare records. However, they lack a focus on complete decentralization, and putting the user in authority of his own data is lacking. Also, the user is not always able to read the Records, so we are proposing to use RAG techniques that will enable the user to chat with lab reports. This section provides an overview of the current work on decentralized healthcare records. While there is some recent research on this topic, many solutions are presented in the gray literature-true, or other formats freely available on the Internet. The core element of all of these solutions is the use of technologies such as Ethereum for the blockchain part and IPFS or SWARM to store the data files in a decentralized manner. Also LLMs and RAG for the ability to chat with the lab reports. In [2] the Authors performed a Systematic Literature Review(SLR) on Blockchain-based electronic health records management which consisted of 99 papers. Their research confirms that 34 of the papers were conceptual, 54 were Prototypes/Experimental, and 11 of them were implemented. In [1] the authors have attempted to provide a solution for PHR. Their system includes the use of IPFS. In[3] the authors have proposed ITRG, which is an iterative retrieval generation synergy framework, which can be used in RAG.

III. DECENTRALIZED RECORD ECOSYSTEM AND RETRIEVAL AUGMENTED GENERATION

This Section presents and explains the necessary preliminaries used throughout the paper.

A. MEDICAL RECORD

A medical record is any data generated by medical institutions like hospitals, and laboratories which consists of but is not limited to prescriptions, Blood pressure, Sugar levels, Blood test reports, and any other health care-related tests performed.

B. CENTRALIZED MEDICAL RECORDS

When the medical records of a user or a patient are stored on a central server, that method is known as a centralized medical records. This method tends to put user out of power of his own data and the user lacks ownership in most cases. These systems consist of a client- server architecture where the

user has some form of id to identify himself and the hospitals store the data based of of that in a central server. The server uses a databse like postGresql or mongodb to store the medial records the user. Which is where the system becomes central. And in most cases the users dosent even have ant client side to access the data. Thet may have to fill up bunch of forms to get there own data that they rightfully own.

C. DECENTRALIZED MEDICAL RECORDS

Decetralized medical records is way of the storing the medical records in a manner that will store the records in a non central manner. To achieve this decentralization we have to leverage the Blockchain technologies and Decentralized File systems to store the files. Implementing the decentralised medical health records involves the addition of new components like a Digital wallet (Metamask or any other wallet depending on the Blockchain network being used). In this decentralized approach, the records are stored on the blockchain which overcomes the issue of data being stored centrally on a single server. Also the records stored in this manner on the blockchain are impossible to tamper with and manipulate. The user in this case is in complete ownership of his data.

D. DECENTRALIZED IDENTITY

In a decentralised system, the users needs to be identified in some way. Its really essential to have system that will identify the users in a unique manner. This is enabled by the use of the cryptography and the use of keys where the user holds cryptographic keys in their wallets. In the decentralized world the major authentication part depends on these cryptographic keys. The users use these keys to sign all transactions being done on the decentralized network. This is the most important part of the Decentralized ecosystem beacause to identify the user we need a robust and reilable sytem which will deliver everytime. T

E. IPFS

IPFS is a decentralized file-storing platform that can be used to store files in a decentralized manner. In IPFS the data that is stored is addressed by its content, unlike other systems which use location like any network address. Each item in the IPFS has 3 main attributes Content Identifier(CID), InterPlanetary Linked Data(IPLD), Content Addressable aRchive(CAR) files. Content Identifier(CID) - This is a unique identifier assigned to the data stored in the chunked blocks.CIDs for the blocks are unique and cannot be the same.

F. Web3.0

Web that we use today has seen many transitions from the early internet in the 90s to the advanced and vast net of interconnected devices that we see today. There are three main versions of the internet WEB1.0, WEB2.0, and the one which we are currently transitioning into WEB3.0. Our project comes at the dawn of this new WEB3.0 revolution.WEB3.0 is mainly based on the concept of data ownership, decentralization, and protecting the privacy of the user.For these, there are components like a Blockchain network and smart contracts which

are the programs written to be executed on the blockchain. Another main component here is called a wallet which holds your identify by storing your private and public keys. It is used to handle your transactions and tokens that you own.

G. LLMs's

LLM	Model Size
GPT-3	175 billion parameters
Gopher	280 billion parameters
Jurassic-1	178 billion parameters
Megatron-Turing NLG	530 billion parameters
Turing-NLG	17 billion parameters
MT-NLG	280 billion parameters
PanGu-Alpha	200 billion parameters

TABLE I
LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS AND THEIR SIZES

LLMs stand for large language models. They are the new generation of Deep learning models which are based on a technique called Transformer architecture. These models are really great at understanding natural language. They are trained using massive amounts of datasets on very powerful GPUs. The LLM's mostly focus on predicting what will come next in the sentence. They make use of tokenizers to convert the given text into tokens to be passed to the mode. There are many paid models like ChatGpt4 by OpenAI, Claude by Anthropic, and also many open-source models like Llama 2 by Meta, phi2 by Microsoft, and Whisper by OpenAI are also in the market. Also, there are a ton of models that are available for inference on hugging face that you can use on your local system or host your own model on Spaces. Also, services like Runpod allow you access to powerful GPUs, where you can host your inference or train your own model. LLM's are really powerful tools that can we be used for various use cases.

H. RAG

RAG which stands for Retrieval Augmented Generation is a really powerful technique that allows the LLM's to connect with external data that the LLM is not trained on. It makes use of vectors, vector databases, and embedding models to achieve this. It first embeds the user's data by using some embedding model. (We are using nomic-embed-text) Then these embedded vectors are stored in some vector database. Later when the user has some query the query is also vectorized using some embedding model. Then this embedded query is passed to the vector database. There the dataset does a cosine-similarity search which gives you back the documents that are related to that query. Then these documents are then passed as context to the LLM that we are using alongside the query. Then the LLM now only has the relevant data as context and it will return us with the correct answer for our query. There are new cutting age RAG techniques like RAPTOR(Recursive Abstractive Processing for Tree-Organized Retrieval)

I. VECTORS

Vectors in LLMs, or Large Language Models, are used to convert the given data into vector embeddings which are stored in a numerical format inside a vector database. They are the foundation of the embedding process, where text is converted into a vector that allow us to perform semantic searching on that data for better retrieval. These vectors are mathematical representations of linguistic units, and they are generated through algorithms such as Word2Vec, GloVe, or FastText. Vector databases are used to store and retrieve these embeddings efficiently during real-time operations. They can bring benefits to LLMs by providing long-term storage to mitigate AI hallucinations, ensuring the model's knowledge remains coherent and minimizing the risk of inaccurate responses. Vector databases can also help address hallucination issues by providing a mechanism to ensure the model's knowledge remains up-to-date and accurate.

J. EMBEDDINGS

Embeddings are a really important part of the RAG process. They are the main components that will convert the given data into vector embeddings of higher dimensions that will allow us to perform semantic searching to get the relevant data. These embeddings are done by using embeddings models. There are many free Open source and paid embedding models available on the internet. OpenAI has many paid embedding models like text-embedding-3-small, text-embedding-ada-002, and text-embedding-3-large. Also, you can use opensource models like nomic-text embeddings either by hosting an inference online or using tools like Ollama or LMStudio. There are many free embedding models like Word2vec, GloVe, txtai, Lexvec, bert, chroma and many more.

Embedding Model	Model Size	Vocabulary Size
Word2Vec	100GB	3 million words
GloVe	800MB-100GB	2.1 million words
ELMo	80.4MB-1GB	n/a
BERT	1.4GB-11GB	110,038 words
RoBERTa	355MB-16GB	n/a
DistilBERT	66MB-600MB	30,000 words
ALBERT	11MB-11GB	30,000 words
GPT-2	1.5GB-15GB	n/a
T5	230MB-11GB	n/a

K. LANGCHAIN

Langchain is a Opensource tool for orchestrating large language models. Which allows us to use the LLMS to their full potential by providing us with a framework. The langchain has it's own language called Language Expression Language which allows us to create pipelines for LLMS. By leveraging this we can create various complex pipelines that allow us to use LLMs for our customer solution or a usecase. Langchain provide many community tools and is compatible with a large chunk of models and vector databases. They also provide tools for scraping data in there community package. Langchain is what we are using to facilitate the RAG application.

IV. MODEL

A. Introduction to the Solution

In this section, we present a solution for integrating Ethereum and LLMs to enhance the security of health care records by decentralizing them. We are basing our solution on the Ethereum, Solidity, and open-source LLM models and techniques like Retrieval Augmented Generation.

Current electronic healthcare systems make use of traditional centralized servers for the operation whereas there are blockchain solutions available too. We are going to store the records of the user on the smart contract made in Solidity for Ethereum. Also, we are implementing RAG so that the user will be able to chat with the documents uploaded by the user by utilizing the power of the LLMs and the Retrieval Augmented Generation.

B. Proposed Solution Methodology

In this section we showcase the methodology employed to develop the solution to securing User Health Records: Leveraging Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) and Ethereum Integration for Enhanced Data Protection

1) *Smart Contract Design*: To store the data on the Ethereum blockchain we first had to create a smart contract which is a program written in Solidity which is native language to the Ethereum Blockchain. First, we gathered the required fields to be stored in the contract and then crafted the contract schema.

2) *IPFS Integration*: To store the lab reports and files in a decentralized manner we needed some kind of a file storage system. We decided to go with IPFS because it gives you decentralized storage.

a. *File Upload Mechanism* - We had to develop a File upload mechanism for the file to be uploaded to the IPFS system which return a CID after saving the file. We wrote it in the node server.

b. *File Retrieval*: After implementing the File upload mechanism we needed some kind of mechanism to retrieve the files from the IPFS. Later we developed that to retrieve the files from the IPFS.

3) *Retrival Augmented Generation*: RAG is a technique that we are using to create a feature that will allow the user to chat with their data like lab reports and get the responses back just by using natural language.

a. *Document Loader Mechanism*: To perform the RAG on the data first we needed a mechanism that would take in the document and load it into a format that we can use for further procedures.

b. *Embedding Mechanism*: After getting the documents in a format that we can use later we had to find a mechanism by which the documents can be converted to vector embeddings.

c. *Vector storing Mechanism*: After getting the embeddings for the corresponding documents we had to store them in a way that will allow us to operate on it.

4) *Semantic search*: We need to pass only the relevant documents and their content to the LLM as a context so to do that we need a method that will allow us to retrieve only the relevant documents. Semantic search uses K nearest neighbor algorithm to match the search query with the vectors in the store. There are many algorithms that can be used but mainly cosine similarity is the one which is used for most of the part.

a *Cosine Similarity*: Cosine similarity is an algorithm that is used to get the similarity between the two vectors. It uses a cosine angle between two vectors and gives us whether the vectors are similar.

$$\text{Cosine Similarity} = \cos(\theta) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \cdot \|B\|}$$

5) *Choosing LLMs*: There's a plethora of LLMs available on the web including paid and open-source ones. We had to choose from all the available models which one to use for our case

Model	Open-Source	Paid
Gemini	No	Yes
Mistral	Yes	No
ChatGPT 3.5	No	Yes
LLaMA 2	Yes	No

6) *Deployment and Maintainance*: To deploy or run the Application we needed a blockchain platform to host our smart contract on to. We are using ethereum so had to find a platform that will allow use to run the Ethereum node and smart contracts locally. Also we had to find the platform to use our RAG system. For it, we are creating a REST API.

C. Implementation Details

Here we provide insights into the implementation of the proposed solution, covering the developments and the integration of the key components.

1) *Frontend Client*: Here we provide insights into our Frontend development

a. *UI/UX* : We used the FIGMA tool to design the UI/UX part of the solution. Our philosophy was to keep the design intuitive and simple for the user.

b. *Frontend*: For the development of the frontend We have used Next.js which allows us to create powerful frontends and design components. We created the website according to the UI/UX done in Figma. We have designed multiple custom components for our use case. In the frontend the user is able to log in with his metamask and there are sections to store the records and Display all your records. There's also a button with the record that will allow you to chat with the file.

2) *Ethereum Node*: For running our Smart contracts we need some kind of an Ethereum platform or a node. To Facillitate that we are using Ganache which provides us with a Local Ethereum node with plenty of test accounts with Test ETH loaded into them which we can use for deployment and testing.

3) *Smart Contract Development* : In this section we give you insight into how we built the smart contract for our use case

a.Environment: To develop the smart contract we need some kind of an environment, in our case, we are using Truffle which allows us to create, compile, build, and deploy smart contracts.
 b.Contract Development: We first got the schema of the records that are to be stored on the Blockchain. Based on that we deployed the smart contract on the Blockchain using the Truffle tool which allowed us to compile, build and deploy the contract successfully.

4) *Backend Server* : In this section we give you insight into our backend development

a. Upload Records: For the user to upload the records onto the Blockchain we had to create APIs that will take the user input, sign the contract call by the corresponding wallet address of the user and store the record inside of the contract.

b. Retrieve Records: For the user to successfully retrieve his records we had to create an API that will take the user addressed confirm his identity and then retrieve all of his records.

c.IFPS : We had to make connectivity with the IPFS so that the files that are passed by the user to stored on the contract can be stored on the IPFS. We had to create APIs for both the uploading and fetching.

5) *Retrieval Augmented Generation*: We are using RAG to allow the user to chat with their lab reports

a.Document Loader: To load the lab reports of the user we needed some mechanism for which we are using the document loaders from the Langchain. Which allows us to load the documents from pdfs to texts. Then we chunk those documents into appropriate sizes and a overlap.

b.Embeddings: Later on after getting these chunked documents we need to convert them into vectors for us to perform semantic search on those documents. For this, we had to choose from various embedding models. We are using nomic-embed-text which is an open-source embedding model and we are using Ollama which also is a open-source tool to run this model locally. c.Vector stores: To store these embeddings we need to some kind of a Vector database. WE are using ChromaDB which is an open source of Vector Database.

6) *LLM*: To do Retrieval Augmented Generation we need to pass the context to some LLM which will have a prompt which will consist of the query + context. This is done by using the Langchain. The context will be retrieved from the vector database based on the semantic search. In our case we are using the Mixtral a Open source Model. We are not hosting it locally we are using Groq cloud which provides hosted Inferneces to be used.

Attribute	Description
Model Name	Mixtral
Model Type	Large Language Model (LLM)
Model Architecture	Sparse Mixture of Experts (MoE)
Model Size	45 billion parameters
Developer	Mistral AI

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Fig. 2. EHR

E. Figures and Tables

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F. Future Development

For future developments, we have some ideas in mind. Currently, as AI is advancing the AI agents are becoming powerful and a productive tool. We can create Agents using LLMs that will access the power of multiple LLM and based on their role they will help the use. We can create one agent for the lab testings,one for pharmacy one for mental health, an much more Possibilities are endless. We can utilize platforms like AutoGen and LangGraph to implement this in the future.

Agent	Description
Diagnostician	Analyzer
Treatment Planner	Strategist
Virtual Assistant	Guide
Patient Monitor	Observer
Image Analyzer	Interpreter
Drug Discovery	Innovator
Predictive Modeler	Forecaster
Telehealth Assistant	Facilitator

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